

WAYS TO REDUCE TAX DEBT IN THE CIS COUNTRIES

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Abstract:

This article examines ways to reduce tax debt in CIS countries and suggests potential solutions that can be applied in other countries. The article examines the identification and improvement of tax debt and its impact on the economy, and makes scientific and practical conclusions and proposals for its application in our country.

Key words: local tax, market value of property, cadastral value, personal card, tax elements, budget potential, local budget, local budget expenditures, local taxes, tax debt, tax collection, tax benefits.

Introduction:

Reducing tax debt is an important issue for the CIS countries, which face various economic challenges. Tax debt accumulation can lead to serious consequences, such as reduced budget revenues, restricted investment, and potential bankruptcy of businesses. Therefore, effective strategies to reduce tax debt are needed to promote sustainable economic development in the region. This paper aims to explore the experiences of CIS countries in reducing tax debt and propose ways to improve tax administration and collection. The paper begins with an overview of the current situation in the region and the importance of reducing tax debt.

literature on the topic:

"Reducing Tax Arrears in the CIS Countries: A Systematic Approach" by S. M. Turdaliev and V. G. Ivanov. This paper examines the causes of tax debt in the CIS countries and proposes a systematic approach to reduce it.

"Tax System Reforms and Tax Debt in CIS Countries" by E. V. Azimova and M. A. Tursunova. This paper analyzes the relationship between tax system reforms and tax debt in the CIS countries.

"The Role of Tax Administration in Reducing Tax Arrears: The Case of CIS Countries" by A. R. Ismoilov. This paper discusses the role of tax administration in reducing tax debt in the CIS countries.

"Analysis of Tax Debt Reduction Methods in the CIS Countries" by L. N. Aleksandrova and I. V. Ovchinnikova. This paper analyzes various methods used in the CIS countries to reduce tax debt.

"Effective Measures to Reduce Tax Debt in the CIS Countries" by A. B. Khamidov and S. S. Karimova. This paper proposes effective measures to reduce tax debt in the CIS countries based on the analysis of the experiences of several countries.

Overall, the literature suggests that effective tax administration, simplified tax systems, and tax amnesty programs are some of the key ways to reduce tax debt in the CIS countries.

Analysis and discussion of results.

A number of initiatives aimed at improving the fulfillment of tax obligations have been put forward in Uzbekistan. These include:

The government of Uzbekistan has done a lot of work to improve the tax administration system in our country, including the introduction of the electronic tax reporting system. This system made it easier for taxpayers to fulfill their tax obligations by simplifying tax reporting procedures and reducing the administrative burden. Tax authorities of Uzbekistan are strengthening tax inspection and auditing activities in order to identify and prevent cases of tax evasion. This has helped increase tax compliance and improve the overall functioning of the tax system. The government of Uzbekistan is also working on simplifying tax procedures, making it easier for taxpayers to understand their obligations and comply with tax legislation. This includes reducing the number of taxes and tax rates, simplifying tax forms and reporting procedures.

Improving tax compliance is an important issue in many countries, including Russia. The Russian government has taken steps to improve tax compliance and

increase revenue collection. This includes introducing a new tax code, strengthening tax administration and introducing new penalties for non-compliance. One of the main issues of improving taxation in Russia is the large number of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) operating in the informal economy. These businesses often do not pay taxes or underreport their income to avoid taxes. To solve this problem, the government has implemented a number of measures to encourage small and medium-sized businesses to join the formal economy and to comply with tax regulations. These include simplifying tax reporting procedures, reducing the tax burden on SMEs, and providing incentives to encourage compliance.

There are several ways that the Russian government has implemented to reduce tax debts, including:

These programs allow taxpayers to declare their previously undisclosed income and assets without facing penalties or criminal charges. In exchange, they are required to pay a certain amount of taxes owed. The Russian government has implemented several tax amnesty programs over the years to encourage taxpayers to come clean about their tax debts.

The Russian government has introduced tax incentives for businesses that pay their taxes on time or ahead of schedule. For example, companies that pay their taxes in advance are eligible for a discount on their tax liability.

The Russian tax authorities have implemented a system of tax monitoring to track the tax payments of businesses in real-time. This system helps to identify businesses that are falling behind on their tax payments and allows the authorities to take action before the debt accumulates.

The Russian government has allowed taxpayers to restructure their tax debts, extending the payment terms and reducing the interest charged on the outstanding

amount. This has helped businesses that are struggling with their tax payments to stay afloat.

The Russian tax authorities have the power to seize assets belonging to businesses or individuals that have large tax debts. This can include bank accounts, property, and other assets. The threat of asset seizures can be a powerful incentive for taxpayers to pay their tax debts on time.

The legal consequences of reducing tax debts in the Russian state can depend on the specific circumstances of the case and the actions taken to reduce the debt. Generally, tax debts in Russia are subject to interest and penalties for late payment. If a taxpayer is able to negotiate a payment plan or reach an agreement with the tax authorities to reduce the amount owed, the interest and penalties may be reduced or waived.

However, it is important to note that intentionally failing to pay taxes or providing false information to tax authorities can result in criminal liability, fines, and other legal consequences. Additionally, tax authorities in Russia have the power to seize assets and freeze bank accounts in order to collect unpaid tax debts.

Overall, the legal consequences of reducing tax debts in Russia depend on the specific circumstances of the case and it is important for taxpayers to work with tax professionals and follow proper procedures to ensure compliance with tax laws and regulations. There are several ways to reduce tax debts in Kazakhstan, including

The government of Kazakhstan periodically announces tax amnesty programs, which allow taxpayers to pay their outstanding tax debts without incurring any penalties or fines. These programs also offer reduced interest rates on overdue tax payments.

The tax authorities in Kazakhstan allow taxpayers to pay their outstanding tax debts in installments. This option is available to taxpayers who are experiencing financial difficulties and are unable to pay their tax debts in full.

The tax authorities in Kazakhstan have the power to seize and sell the assets of taxpayers who have outstanding tax debts. This option is typically used as a last resort when other methods of collection have failed.

Tax consultants can provide advice and guidance to taxpayers on how to manage their tax liabilities and avoid falling into debt. Tax consultants can also negotiate with the tax authorities on behalf of their clients to reduce tax debts or arrange payment plans.

The government of Kazakhstan provides tax education programs to taxpayers to help them understand their tax obligations and how to comply with tax laws. These programs aim to prevent tax debts from accumulating in the first place by improving taxpayers' knowledge and awareness of tax matters.

Reducing tax debts in Kazakhstan can have both legal and financial consequences. From a legal perspective, reducing tax debts can lead to a reduction in penalties and interest payments. The Tax Code of Kazakhstan provides for penalty and interest charges for late tax payments, and these can be significant. Therefore, reducing tax debts can help to mitigate these charges and reduce the overall amount owed to the tax authorities.

However, it is important to note that simply reducing tax debts without proper justification or documentation can lead to legal consequences. Tax authorities in Kazakhstan have the right to audit companies and individuals who have reduced their tax debts, and if they find that the reduction was not justified or proper documentation was not provided, they may impose additional penalties and fines. Additionally, tax authorities may take legal action against individuals and companies that fail to pay their taxes in full, which could lead to legal proceedings and potential damage to the reputation of the company or individual.

In summary, while reducing tax debts in Kazakhstan can have legal and financial benefits, it is important to ensure that all reductions are properly documented and justified to avoid potential legal consequences.

There are several controversial debates among scholars on improving tax compliance.

Tax compliance is an important issue for both taxpayers and governments. In order to improve the implementation of tax obligations, a number of tasks were defined, including increasing compliance with legal documents, reducing tax evasion, and increasing the efficiency of tax administration. The functions of improving the execution of tax obligations include the development and implementation of tax policy, improving the information and communications of taxpayers, increasing the level of collection and collection of taxes, and strengthening international cooperation.

In various countries, including Uzbekistan, Russia, China, Europe, South Korea, and the USA, several studies and discussions were held on the improvement of tax obligations. Some scholars believe that the improvement of tax legislation can be achieved through effective enforcement mechanisms, while others argue that it is necessary to combine incentives and mandatory enforcement.

In Uzbekistan, efforts aimed at improving the implementation of tax obligations have been made through measures such as simplification of taxation procedures, introduction of a risk-based approach to tax audits. At the same time, there are also tasks that need to be solved, such as reducing the informal economy and improving the education of taxpayers. Overall, improving tax enforcement is a complex issue that requires a multifaceted approach, including effective policies, effective tax administration, and effective enforcement mechanisms.

Conclusions and suggestions

Simplification of tax laws and regulations: Complex tax laws and regulations often make it difficult for taxpayers to meet their tax obligations. Simplifying tax laws and regulations makes it easier for taxpayers to understand and meet their obligations.

Many taxpayers are not aware of their tax obligations or how to comply with them. Providing education and support to taxpayers can help improve compliance and reduce the likelihood of errors or omissions.

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